

A Study on Empowerment of Women using Information and Communication Technology (ICT)

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Abstract

Information and communication technology (ICT) is an integral part of life in the 21st century. Studies suggest a wide range of ICT applications for education and learning, digital media and empowerment of women. The role of ICT in education is to acquire the required skills that can be used in education and learning process. However, there are subtle drawbacks to women and girls in accessing and using information technology. The need of the hour is therefore to become accustomed to the various tools that can be used to improve personal well-being and social status in the society. In the present study, questionnaires were distributed to 100 students belonging to Arts department. The results obtained were subjected to data analysis. Descriptive statistics was used to analyze the data. Most of the respondents were aged from 17 to 23 years respectively. Majority of the respondents were highly competent in using smart phones (47%) and communication (44%). While, their competency was average or low in the use of spreadsheet (65%). It is quite clear that respondents are more compatible with smart phones than computers. It is therefore suggested that students should be given more computer training to maximize their computer skills, as smart phones have their own limitations in ICT.

Keywords: Information and Communication Technology, ICT, Information Technology, Digital media, Education, Women empowerment

Introduction

The rapid growth in the use of information and communication technologies (ICTs) has brought about a stunning change in the 21st century and has affected modern society's demands. ICT is becoming more and more important both in everyday life and in education systems. ICT tools are specifically used to increase access to education, strengthen the relevance of education to an increasingly digital workplace, improve the quality of education, facilitate teaching and learning in a committed, active process connected with real life (Andoh, 2012). Globalization and technological change have created a new global economy "driven by technology, information and knowledge" (US Department of Labor, 1999).

ICT is one of the most powerful tools of human invention that can transform lifestyle patterns, facilitate learning and create a wide range of opportunities in educational, industrial, digital and IT sectors. In the present scenario, it is essential to acquire the necessary skills to keep abreast of changing technological trends regardless of

age or gender. However, with the world rapidly moving into digital media and information, the role of ICT in education is becoming increasingly important and this importance will continue to grow and develop in the 21st century. Education is the process of learning or acquiring knowledge that depends entirely on the quality of teachers. According to futurist Alvin Toffler, “The illiterate of the 21st century will not be those who cannot read and write, but those who cannot learn, unlearn and relearn.

The influence of ICT has certainly brought tremendous impact in women’s empowerment. The empowerment of women means increasing the spiritual, political, social, educational, gender or economic strength of the individuals. There are a number of ways to improve women’s economic status through trade, governance, education and health. It also brings countless openings, including small enterprises, self help groups (SHGs), etc. In India, women’s empowerment depends heavily on many different variables, including geographical location, social status and age. Impoverishment, illiteracy, lack of computer literacy and language barriers are factors that inhibit access to ICT infrastructure, especially in developing countries. Another barrier to ICT is the lack of access to women (Arrawatia and Meel, 2012). Most women suffer due to the inaccessibility and use of ICT tools due to lack of infrastructure and incapacity.

However, this study primarily focuses on the use of ICT tools in education and learning process. It also examines how information technology in education creates more learning environments centered on students, which often create tensions for teachers and students. Therefore, educational institutions are increasingly required to use ICT to provide students with skills and knowledge. This study aims to determine students’ skills in the use of electronic devices such as basic computers and smart phones. The research was carried out using a quantitative method for the collection of data with the following objectives:

Students’ demographics (age, class, use of computers and mobile phones)

- Students’ perceived skills in ICT
- Students’ application of ICT in education and learning process

Review of literature

- Wadi and Sonia (2002) emphasized improving the quality of education and training, especially during education expansion. In many ways, ICTs can improve the quality of education by increasing motivation and engagement of learners, facilitating the acquisition of basic skills and enhancing teacher training.
- Wheeler (2008) reported information technology as a tool for transforming women’s lives and as a supposed enabler of empowerment.
- Hew & Brush (2007) outlined about the attitudes and beliefs of teachers have an impact on the successful integration of ICT into education.
- Keong et al. (2005) studied the use of information and communication technology in teaching mathematics. They stressed the need for teacher training and the integration of ICT in the curriculum.
- Arrawatia and Meel (2012) emphasized information and communication technology & empowerment of women in India. They addressed the prospects of ICT-supported women’s empowerment networking processes.
- Mavura (2015) highlighted ICT for girls and women empowerment. She addressed women’s empowerment is a key factor in determining success of development.

Methodology

Participants

The present study was carried out in a private college. 100 students belonging to arts department participated in this investigation. The age group of students ranged from 19 to 21 years respectively.

Data Collection Methods

Individual student participants were given questionnaires personally. They were asked to submit within a day A total of 100 questionnaires were collected back from the students with 100% return rate. The collected questionnaires were subjected to data analysis.

Instrument

The first section of the questionnaire contains students' demographic information based on gender, age, computer knowledge and smart phone experience, etc. The second section focused on their knowledge and skills in the use of ICT. Then, the respondents were asked to assess the use of ICT in the learning process. A reliability test was used to determine the internal consistency of items in the questionnaire by using Cronbach's Alpha reliability test (Cronbach, 1951). The test was performed using Cronbach alpha statistics software v1.0.5 (Wessa, 2017). Cronbach's alpha coefficient was found to be 0.992 (arts students). The alpha value of 0.90 is considered excellent, 0.80 very good, and .070 acceptable (Kline, 2005).

Data Analyses

Data was analyzed using descriptive statistics to calculate the frequencies of the collected data. In this study, the variables observed showed good internal consistency.

Results:

Demographic information of respondents (Arts students)

Teachers' demographic information comprising of respondents age, computer knowledge and smart phone experience are given in Table 1. Of the 100 respondents, 47% of the respondents (1-2 years) showed smartphone experience while 30% of the students (5-6 years) exhibited proficiency in using computers.

Demographic information of students (Arts department)

Variable	Category (Years)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Respondents	Arts students	100	100%
Age	17-18	36	36
	19-20	37	37
	21-22	27	27
	21-22	27	27
Computer knowledge	1-2	31	27
	3-4	38	32
	5-6	19	30
	7 and above	Nil	11

Smartphone Experience	1-2	47	47
	3-4	29	28
	5-6	38	29
	7 and above	3	9

Students' perceived skills in ICT

Respondents were asked to rate their ICT skills on a four-point Likert-type scale ranging from "Cannot use/none (1)" to "High (4)".

As presented in Table 2, majority of the respondents were highly competent in smart phones (47%) and communication (E-mail) (44%). While, most respondents perceived their skills in the spreadsheet as low or cannot use (65%).

Table 2
Descriptive Statistics of Respondents (Arts students) Perceived ICT Skills

ICT Skills	Cannot use (%)	Low (%)	Moderate (%)	High (%)
Word processor	28	16	23	33
Spreadsheet	65	17	7	11
Presentation	38	29	19	14
Search engines	23	27	18	32
Communication (e.g. E-mail)	17	13	26	44
Smartphones (e.g. Google Apps)	13	15	25	47

Cronbach alpha=0.828

Discussion

ICT has brought enormous significance in diverse fields such as information technology, digital media, industrial and educational sectors, research and development, etc. The use of ICT tools in enhancing skills in various sectors has completely revolutionized in the development process. ICT in empowering women's growth has provided spiritual, educational and economic strength of individuals in the society. Mavura (2015a) stressed on empowerment of women in determining development success. Studies show that women suffer from various problems due to lack of education and information. Different types of ICT tools like radio, television, mobile phone and the Internet are used to provide awareness, education and information among women. This knowledge can therefore create a lot of opportunities. It is apparent that the future of any nation depends on youth irrespective of their caste, creed or gender. This paper thus primarily discusses on the influence of electronic gadgets such as computers and smartphones used by women students in education and learning process.

In the present study, most students showed high skills in the use of smartphones and communication. In contrast, most respondents had a low preference for spreadsheet applications. It is therefore obvious that respondents excelled in smartphones compared to computers in the education and learning process. Though, applications of computers are indispensable in the learning process it is interesting to note that the student respondents are more comfortable with smartphones, as they are user friendly. Another probable reason may be due to non-affordability or economic conditions and linguistic barriers. The findings are in agreement with Mavura (2015b), who reported that girls and women have less access to technology, thereby significantly reducing educational and economic opportunities. It is also important to develop programs to teach girls at an

early stage using computers and tablets. According to Arrawatia and Meel (2012), the knowledge available in the global scenario is in English language and the downtrodden communities could not understand. This obviously makes it difficult to acquire the universal knowledge.

Proper education, together with knowledge, secure jobs and a physical strength can transform the future of a woman from being a fragile, submissive, marginalized, suppressed, voiceless, inferior creature to an independent, strong, positive, exuberant and progressive one. Since education is student-centered and teachers are the stake holders, the present z and skills of future generations are to be developed through ICT and other pedagogical technologies.

Through information technology and its applications women have crossed borders rendering yeoman services proving their capacities in plethora of genres. Various Apps such as Google Classroom, Kahoot, Edmodo, Khan Academy, MOOC, NPTEL, Swayam and many more have laid down concrete platforms/forums that have made teaching and learning process more conducive, effective, and, facilitative. As every student is glued to smartphones and tabs, teaching through such devices motivates and triggers interest, even in the less interested students.

Though, it is a known fact that every classroom consists of students with mixed abilities and the teacher cannot cater to the personal needs of every individual. However, these gaps can be filled by applying innovative, multifarious and user friendly Apps which empowers them to meet the new challenges and revolutionize the whole gamut of education both at the primary, secondary and higher education levels.

This study clearly indicates that most of the respondents frequently used smartphones and integrated google application software in the learning processes. However, the result of this study shows the usage of computer software applications were decreased in learning processes by student respondents. According to Arrawatia and Meel (2012), the use of ICT in learning enables girls and women to receive quality education leading to personal development, which helps them to manage their lives independently. Thus, it is suggested that students should be given adequate hands-on training on how to integrate and use ICT in the learning process.

Conclusion

This study has clearly demonstrated that the success of ICT in education and learning process is not about computer or software but influencing and empowering women students to acquire requisite computer skills through training programmes and workshops during the course of their study programme right from their entry level. This initiative will certainly enhance students' capabilities to acquire ICT skills effectively and it will enable them with employment opportunities.

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